
Taraba State Based Journalists Perception of Investigative Journalism as an Antidote to Institutional Corruption in Nigeria

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Abstract

The researchers examined the use of investigative journalism in combating institutional corruption in Nigeria. It investigated the challenges affecting investigative journalists in curbing institutional corruption in Nigeria. The researchers employed the social responsibility theory which posited that the mass media have a duty to serve the public interest by providing accurate and unbiased information, promoting democratic values and holding those in power accountable. The researchers adopted a qualitative approach where an in-depth interview was employed alongside 20 journalists from a population of 100 from six chapels within Jalingo metropolis who write for the various news organisations in the State. The findings of the study revealed that journalists in Taraba State have misconceptions regarding what institutional corruption entails which has affected their fight against institutional corruption. Also, it was established that challenges such as fear of the unknown, harassment, lack of access to information, lack of funds and widespread corruption within the media amongst others. The researchers recommended among others that there is need for journalists to be enlightened on what institutional corruption entails through organising seminars and symposiums. It further recommended that journalists should prioritise investigative reporting that exposes corrupt practices within institutions as that would help reduce the rate of corrupt practices in Nigeria.

Keywords: Investigative Journalism, Corruption, Institutional Corruption, Journalists, Nigeria